

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

PRESENTATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF THE PRINCIPLES OF THE CONSTITUTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

Gadirov A.

Associate Professor of Law Department of the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, PhD in Law

Abstract

It is known that in parallel with the change of social life, the values formed in humans change the essence of social relations. This, in turn, leads to certain changes in the form and nature of the criminal proceedings. Thus, opinions on the necessity of changing the legal norms ensuring the legal regulation of newly-arranged and modified issues are voiced. In this article, in this respect, the main advantage of being a legal-legal act is that it is operative, reacting immediately to the changes.

The article analyzes the main trends of the constitutional-legal regulation of the criminal proceedings and sets out specific ideas for improving the legislation in this area.

Criminal procedural law contains the legal norms regulating criminal-procedural legal relations. According to the theory of law, criminal-procedural legal relations can be viewed in two ways: broad and narrow. In the broader meaning of the legal relationship, the form of special social interaction is understood to have occurred objectively before the law. In a narrow sense, the word "legal relationship" is understood to be one of the types of social relationships that the law norms set.

Keywords: criminal procedure, judicial proceedings, justice, personality rights, procedural sanctions, procedural form, constitutional principles.

The principles of criminal proceedings are significant and leading provisions that are reflected in the legal norms of criminal procedure law. But in general, it should be noted that the principles of the criminal process - unlike other criminal procedure rules, a crime of a general and defining nature - are procedural rules, they acquire the specificity, accuracy of various institutions of the criminal process and more special procedural rules related to its various stages. The principles of the criminal process are an important determinant for all procedural forms and institutions and reflect more significant features and aspects of the criminal process.

Relying on the fundamental law of the state - the Constitutional basis and enshrined as the guiding rules of the criminal process, the principles of criminal proceedings, giving a special order to the presence of procedural relations, at the same time also dictates the main elements of the procedural and legal status of the individual, in unity with other legal means express it in a clear form .

First of all, it should be noted that during the determination of the principles of the criminal process, attention should be directed not only to the forced subjects of the criminal process - the settlement of legal relations between persons representing the bodies carrying out criminal prosecution, but also to protection. Strategic settlement of procedural relations between leading persons and persons (citizens), regardless of their will, for one reason or another involved in the field of criminal proceedings is also important. In this sense, the principles of the criminal process, first of all, should reflect in themselves on the basis of what rules or in what form the "treatment" by the state body carrying out criminal prosecution with the subject of the defense side is carried out (4, p. 21).

The criminal procedural legislation defines common for all subjects of the criminal process and specific rights and obligations for an individual subject. In the

Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the status of all participants in the process, including rights and obligations, is determined by separate articles named after them. Almost all participants use the same method: their rights and obligations are listed in paragraphs and the rights and obligations not listed in these paragraphs, defined in other norms of the Code of Criminal Procedure are indicated. The latter are reflected in the norms defining the principles of criminal proceedings and the provisions governing the individual stages of the process. In general, as noted, the inaccurate number and environment of the principles prevents the creation of unisexuality in determining the rights and obligations of the participants in the process. Thus, they are either indicated directly or expressed in another specific form, or they come from the significance of the norms governing various procedures, investigative actions involving the subject, etc.

Let us now turn our attention to the characteristics of certain principles of criminal justice. These are the principle of respect for the honor and dignity of the individual, the principle of ensuring the right to inviolability of the personal life of a person, the principle of the presumption of innocence, the principle of objectivity, impartiality and fairness of criminal proceedings, the principle of ensuring the rights and freedoms of man and citizen enshrined in the Constitution, a comprehensive, complete and objective investigation of the circumstances of the case and principles of transparency in criminal proceedings.

As noted, the first of these principles is the principle of respect for the honor and dignity of the individual, this principle, like some principles, has a constitutional basis. Thus, in the 46th article of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan it is noted that everyone has the right to protect their honor and dignity of the person protected by the state. Nothing can serve as a basis for humiliating the dignity of a person. At the

same time, in the 3rd paragraph of this article it is noted that no one can be subjected to torture and torture. No one may be subjected to treatment or punishment that degrades human dignity (1). The noted principle is recognized as the natural rights of people. The honor and dignity of a person is considered the highest human value of law. In accordance with the "World Declaration of Human Rights" of the United Nations of December 10, 1948 and the International Covenant "On Civil and Political Rights" of December 16, 1966, at the same time identified by the European Convention "On protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms", the right to respect for personal and family life, it is noted that everyone has the right to protection of honor and dignity, nothing can serve as a reason to humiliate the dignity of an individual. In criminal law, the object of a crime is directly the honor, dignity and business reputation of another person. Honor is a public assessment of a person, as a member of society, determined by moral, spiritual, cultural qualities, for the attitude towards other individuals, the state and society. Honor is a public assessment of a citizen, as a member of society about its social aspects, moral qualities. Thus, once again it became clear that the concept of honor is associated with the assessment of the individual by society in terms of its spiritual qualities. Even in the Plenary Resolution of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the practice of application by courts of legislation on the protection of honor and dignity" dated May 14, 1999, it is noted that based on the fact that the right to protect honor and dignity is a constitutional right to explain to the courts that interested persons for the protection of honor and dignity can file a claim directly in court without an initial appeal to give a refutation in the media (7). Of course, this principle should be ensured not only by the courts, but also by the primary investigation bodies. moral qualities. Thus, once again it became clear that the concept of honor is associated with the assessment of the individual by society in terms of its spiritual qualities. Even in the Plenary Resolution of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the practice of application by courts of legislation on the protection of honor and dignity" dated May 14, 1999, it is noted that based on the fact that the right to protect honor and dignity is a constitutional right to explain to the courts that interested persons for the protection of honor and dignity can file a claim directly in court without an initial appeal to give a refutation in the media (7). Of course, this principle should be ensured not only by the courts, but also by the primary investigation bodies. moral qualities. Thus, once again it became clear that the concept of honor is associated with the assessment of the individual by society in terms of its spiritual qualities. Even in the Plenary Resolution of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the practice of application by courts of legislation on the protection of honor and dignity" dated May 14, 1999, it is noted that based on the fact that the right to protect honor and dignity is a constitutional right to explain to the courts that interested persons for the protection of honor and dignity can file a claim directly in court without an initial appeal to give a refutation in the media (7). Of course, this principle

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Another principle is to ensure the right to privacy. In connection with the importance of this principle, it should be noted that in the cases against Azerbaijan considered by the European Court of Human Rights, the violations identified mainly come from non-compliance with the requirements of national legislation on the application of an arrest warrant in judicial practice, incorrect - on the basis of modern standards of interpretation of criminal procedural rules, and in some cases gaps and inconsistencies in the regulation of the application of an arrest warrant. Paragraph 1 of Article 5 of the European Convention requires that any deprivation of liberty must comply with the purpose of Article 5, that is, it must comply with the purpose of the principle of protecting persons from arbitrariness. In this case, the significant issue is not only the "right of freedom" of the individual, but also the "right of immunity". A person "in relation to whom measures of deportation or extradition have been applied" and arrest falling under paragraph 1 (f) of paragraph 5 of Article in the case of *Garayev v. Azerbaijan* (*Garayev v. Azerbaijan*) The Court noted that in the absence of clear legal norms in the national legislation determining the sentencing of arrest, the terms of detention and the extension of this period "for the purpose of extradition", *Garayev's* deprivation of liberty did not meet the standards of "quality of law" required on the basis of the Convention and, accordingly, this deprivation was considered a violation of Article 5 paragraph 1 (f) (8). It follows from the above case that the domestic legal system failed to protect the applicant from unjustified imprisonment, because there was no legal rule governing the procedure for detention pending extradition, foreseeing the consequences in advance (6, p. 5).

The presumption of innocence is one of the important principles of criminal proceedings, and it should be noted that this principle is also reflected in our Constitution. The importance of the presumption of innocence for the bodies carrying out the primary investigation - the investigator, the prosecutor, etc. is that one of the requirements of the "presumption of innocence" during the conduct of a criminal case before trial is a comprehensive and thorough investigation of the circumstances of the case. At the same time, attention should be paid to one issue that this principle provides broad rights of self-defense of the accused and violation of this provision by the investigator or prosecutor, that is, the requirement to prove innocence from the accused contradicts the essence of this principle (for example, the requirement to provide an alibi, etc.). d.).

With regard to the presumption of innocence, the European Court of Human Rights on the existing issue determined that the members of the court, in the exercise of their powers, should not act from the position that the accused is guilty of the crime of which he is accused. In this regard, the right of the last word belongs to the verdict of the court. In connection with the presumption of innocence, M.S. Strogovich notes that the significance of the presumption of innocence as an objective legal provision is that innocent persons are protected from unfounded accusations and are not convicted without full, undeniable and without prejudice confirmation of guilt (2, p. 396).

Courts at trials are obliged to consider court cases and materials related to criminal prosecution only on the basis of facts corresponding to legal procedures reflected in the appropriate form in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, impartially and fairly. Naturally, we are talking about the principle of objectivity, impartiality and fairness of criminal proceedings. The criminal process is conducted in such a way that at each current stage there is an opportunity to check the decisions made and the actions taken at the previous stage. This is an important condition for ensuring the interests of law and law. But, the structure of the process or the stage structure does not answer the question of what and how exactly the interests of law and law are ensured. The fact is that every action and decision taken in the process can be appealed by the participants in the process, and the duty of the prosecutor or the court, in the presence of such a complaint or absence, is to verify that the case was comprehensively, completely and impartially investigated. It is this fulfillment of duty that characterizes the maintenance of this principle. It should also be noted that the rights and obligations inherent in the court allow for effective control of the quality of the primary investigation. In addition, we note that the impartiality of the court requires refraining from taking sides; impartiality, being subjective and objective, is divided into two categories - subjective impartiality is the personal impartiality of a judge, in such cases, the legislation provides for a mechanism of "objection against the judge". But, the biased attitude of the judge must be proven. Otherwise, the judge's attitude is considered impartial. And objective impartiality requires that there are no objective cases, facts that cause the biased attitude of the judge. If such cases are present, then it is possible to consider the objective bias of the judge in that case. For example, if the defendant has specific connections with the judge in charge of the case, then there is an objective bias. In national law, and for such cases, the mechanism of objection is used. The absence of an objection mechanism in the national legislation for the European Court is a violation of fair judicial law (5, p. 140). biased attitude of the judge must be proven. Otherwise, the judge's attitude is considered impartial. And objective impartiality requires that there are no objective cases, facts that cause the biased attitude of the judge. If such cases are present, then it is possible to consider the objective bias of the judge in that case. For example, if the defendant has specific connections with the judge in charge of the case, then there is an objective bias. In national law, and for such cases, the mechanism of objection is used. The absence of an objection mechanism in the national legislation for the European Court is a violation of fair judicial law (5, p. 140). biased attitude of the judge must be proven. Otherwise, the judge's attitude is considered impartial. And objective impartiality requires that there are no objective cases, facts that cause the biased attitude of the judge. If such cases are present, then it is possible to consider the objective bias of the judge in that case. For example, if the defendant has specific connections with the judge in charge of the case, then there is an objective bias. In national law, and for such cases, the mechanism of objection is used. The absence

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Scientist M.A. Jafarkuliev believes that the principle of a comprehensive, complete and objective investigation of cases of a case combines three significant provisions of the criminal process.

A) Completeness - identification of all cases significant for the correct decision of the case;

C) Comprehensiveness - the creation and verification of all possible assumptions related to the case, the verification of all cases that expose and justify the accused, facilitate and aggravate his responsibility, the crime - significant from the point of view of law, the definition of the incident under investigation as it really was, etc.

C) Objectivity - investigation of the actions of the case, as it actually was, impartially and accurately, and making a decision that is fully consistent with the revealed objective facts (3, p.156-157).

We can conclude that all fundamental human rights and freedoms, reduced to separate legal spheres, concretized and conditions for implementation determined by the Constitution, are also defined in the sphere of criminal procedure. The main features of these rights in the field of criminal proceedings are that they are not directly exercised by the persons themselves, the participants in the criminal process, this requires the actions of the bodies carrying out the process provided for by law. Therefore, ensuring the rights of persons in the field of criminal process to a greater extent depends not on the personal initiative of the participants in the process, but on the activities of the bodies conducting the process. In this regard, following the basics of applying procedural mandatory actions is the main condition for ensuring the rights of the individual. These foundations are provided for in Article 147, which defines the use of detention in criminal proceedings, coercive measures used for the production of procedural actions, as well as separate articles defining specific conditions for coercive procedural action Code of Criminal Procedure. From the point of view of ensuring the legal and legitimate interests of persons participating in the criminal process, strict adherence to the procedures of the law when applying specific coercive

actions is of particular importance. Following such procedures, on the one hand, if it leads to the desired result, on the other hand, does not exclude coercion, ensures coercion to a degree serving the duties of criminal proceedings. Compliance with the law of procedural coercive actions applied to a suspect or accused directly depends on the legality and validity of the suspicion or accusation brought against a particular person. Groundlessness of suspicions or accusations automatically makes procedural coercive actions groundless. So, procedural authorities should pay serious attention to the detention or arrest, which are characterized by particular acuteness, otherwise there can be no question of the principles of ensuring the rights and freedoms of man and citizen. Let's expand this idea a little more, the principle of ensuring the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen, which is reflected in the Criminal Procedure Code, is also the leading idea that ensures the fundamental right as a person - to be subjected to torture and ill-treatment, subject to inhuman punishment or punishment degrading. Even given the importance of this principle in the case of *Aksoy v. Turkey* (December 18, 1996,

The openness of criminal proceedings comes from the Article 127 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, expressed from the fifth part of the article. In accordance with the requirements of the article, in all courts, record keeping must be open. Consideration of a case at a closed session may be permitted only if the presumably open court proceedings may cause the disclosure of state, professional and commercial secrets, or is determined by the need to preserve the secrecy of the personal or family life of citizens. But one point needs to be noted here. As reflected in the Law "On Courts and Judges", the provision "In all cases, court decisions must be publicly announced", in our opinion, contradicts the requirements of the principle of openness. We want to explain this question with a simple example. Suppose that the case related to rape was considered at a closed court session and an appropriate decision was made on the case. Naturally, there is nothing illegal here, but if we take into account what and as mentioned above, there is a provision in the legislation "the decision of the courts is openly announced", which reflects the essence of the principle of openness, in this case we want to emphasize one nuance. If persons have the opportunity to get acquainted with at least part of the result of the decision made by the court (in practice, there are even cases of full announcement of the decision), the question arises, if the case is considered closed, then why is the result openly announced? there is a provision in the legislation "the decision of the courts is openly announced", which reflects the essence of the principle of openness, in this case we want to emphasize one nuance. If persons have the opportunity to get acquainted with at least part of the result of the decision made by the court (in practice, there are even cases of full announcement of the decision), the question arises, if the case is considered closed, then why is the result openly announced? there is a provision in the legislation "the decision of the courts is openly announced", which reflects the essence of the principle of

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If the goal is to keep a secret related to personal or family life, we consider it expedient to provide by law that only persons in a closed circle have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the decision of the court at a closed session.

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